

GUQINSONGEST: A MULTIMODAL AND HISTORICALLY GROUNDED DATASET OF GUQIN PLAYING TECHNIQUES

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces GuqinSonGest¹, a multimodal dataset of guqin isolated playing techniques which is derived from a 9th century Chinese treatise, the Tang Chen-zhuo Zhifa (唐陈拙指法). GuqinSonGest is a dataset for comparative analysis: it contains audio and video samples of playing techniques subject to elementary gestural variations, which we denote by *subtechniques*. We motivate the construction of GuqinSonGest by emphasizing the significant yet ambiguous gesture–timbre relationships in guqin compositions, pedagogy, and historical guqin writings. We accumulate around three hours of audiovisual materials, containing samples from five families of playing techniques with systematically varied subtechniques and a full-length guqin piece. We validate the timbral variability caused by differing gestural subtechniques by computationally testing a few gesture–timbre hypothesis.

1. INTRODUCTION

The guqin, commonly abbreviated as qin, is one of the oldest musical instruments in China. The earliest instance of guqin was excavated from the Tomb of Marquis Yi of Zeng (曾侯乙墓), dating back to 433 BCE. Since then, the instrument has gradually evolved into its modern appearance: as shown in Figure 1. Seven strings, made of silk or nylon material, are strapped onto a wooden soundboard of around 120 cm long, 20 cm wide and 5 cm thick. A qin is placed flat on table and played with bare hands. The right hand is used for sound production— plucking, flicking, strumming—whereas the left hand may press, tap, or slide on the string. Chinese literati have long praised the soft sounds of qin; its rich harmonics; and its capacity for fine-grained pitch glide with long sustain, thanks to its length that grants large spatial interval between notes. Accounts of qin are found in an abundant repository of literary mentions, poetry, and vocal accompaniment/solo instrumental compositions [2, 3].

Hundreds of playing techniques of qin have been named and defined throughout history, thanks in part to a special notational system: Jianzi Pu (减字谱), which reflects hand placement and gesture. Each symbol in Jianzi Pu can be

¹ Link to the dataset: <https://zenodo.org/records/14962054>

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Figure 1. Top and side view of modern guqin, with 13 markings (Hui 徽) and seven strings. The right side bridge is called YueShan (岳山). Diagram from [1].

deconstructed into parts, corresponding to left hand and right hand respectively. Consequently, playing techniques are distinguished in terms of fingering, directionality, and dynamics. For accuracy in execution and conciseness in notation, they are named accordingly.

It is also of particular interest to study the musical gestures and timbre of qin because of the ubiquitous reference to causality in qin pedagogy (a good gesture and mindset is indispensable to yielding the “correct” sound). There exists a plethora of historical accounts in defining playing techniques and recommending timbre aesthetics precisely; yet, paradoxically the language used to describe them can be ambiguous and metaphoric. For this reason, studying qin gesture–timbre relationship is expected to benefit from collection of audiovisual data acquired from the real world. From there, the field of music information retrieval (MIR) offers powerful computational tools for analyzing musical timbre and investigating correlations between signals across different modalities [4].

To bridge the gap between semantic and signal-level descriptions of gestures and sounds, our goal is to digitize and concretize the sonic implications in historical guqin gesture–timbre writings. The closest existing dataset that would serve this purpose is the GQ39 dataset [5], comprising 39 excerpts of guqin music annotated by left and right hand playing techniques and note event context. Pairs of gesture–timbre data is available thanks to the already rich gestural information implicit in the playing technique nomenclature. Yet, rigorous study of gesture–timbre relationship calls for a specially designed dataset. First, visual data acquisition is indispensable to offering accurate and

continuous descriptors of gestures. Second, the corpus of audio samples should have carefully-controlled gestural attributes to isolate as much as possible the effects from individual gestural degrees of freedom. We design and record an audiovisual dataset of isolated, short, representative qin sounds labeled by gestural data. In doing so, we also aim to refine within the often oversimplified vocabulary of playing techniques in the field of MIR.

The rest of the article is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the ancient Chinese treatise and how we extracted from text the key gestural subtechniques for each family of playing technique. Section 3 documents the process of dataset design and acquisition. Section 4 establishes a few hypothesis of guqin gesture–timbre relationships and demonstrates how audio features extracted from GuqinSonGest could faithfully reflect them. Lastly, we conclude with remaining challenges and future directions.

2. THE TANG CHENZHUO ZHIFA

Numerous ancient texts dating back to the late IX-th century provided gestural guidelines of defined guqin playing techniques and recommendations on timbre aesthetics [6, 7]. The level of physical clarity provided in these texts vary drastically. In *Zuo You Shou Er Shi Shi Tu Shuo* (左右手二十式图说) [8], the right hand gesture is compared with the posture of a mallard taking off. A certain aesthetics of solitude and elegance is hinted. Yet, the room for imagination and interpretation is boundless. In stark contrast is a treatise called *Tang Chenzhuo Zhifa* (唐陈拙指法) [9] written by Chen Zhuo (陈拙), a qin player and scholar from the Tang dynasty. The treatise covered fine motor instructions on 109 right hand and 107 left hand techniques, as well as advices on their respective timbral aesthetics [2]. More importantly, he distinguished between the right and wrong ways of executing a number of widely-used techniques and their timbral consequences, implicating a causal relationship between minute difference in gestures and sound characteristics. Organized into fifteen chapters, the treatise covers three fundamental elements of qin playing: 指 (finger), 声 (sound), 韵 (resonance). Under each, two of the three subsections: 诀 (technique), 法 (variations), 用 (application) are there to elaborate on the specific usages. Despite a large part of the treatise has been lost over the years, what remained was sufficiently detailed to influence and instruct qin playing to this day [10]. In her PhD dissertation, Dr. Liyu You translated *Tang Chenzhuo Zhifa* into French, and offered a practice-based, computationally-grounded interpretation of the treatise [2]. Our work builds upon You’s interpretation and takes her previous effort of enacting the ancient treatise one step towards completion.

The following subsections demonstrate the level of physical precision in *Tang Chenzhuo Zhifa*, as well as how we identify the important gestural subtechniques from textual accounts. These identified subtechniques will then be systematically varied in the recording plan and thus provide opportunities to study the individual impact of each factor on the resulting timbre. We focus on five families of singular (non-composite) techniques: open string, harmonics,

double notes, vibrato, and glissando. For each technique, the identified gestural subtechniques are summarized in Table 2.

2.1 Open string sounds 散声

On nail use:

凡抹勾打，指当曲，不可大直，甲肉相伴。When it comes to inward plucking techniques (“mo” or “gou” or “da”), finger should slightly bend and cannot be too straight. Attack should be half-nail half-flesh.

凡擘，尤贵用肉。当斜指使弦自使指面上过，擘出向岳。

During outward plucking with thumb, mostly use flesh. Lean the thumb such that the landing is tilted and attack towards YueShan.

挑必甲尖，弦必悬落

Outward plucking with index finger uses nail tip. During attack, index finger drops from hovering above the string instead of leaning on the string.

On positions:

声分刚柔：每弦取声，自有刚柔相应，指往上为刚，刚声清远；指往下为柔，柔声和润。

Pluck sound timbres can be hard or soft: Pluck close to bridge, the sound is powerful and resonates long; pluck away from bridge, the sound is soft and harmonious.

右指靠弦则音钝而木

If right finger lingers too long on string during attack, then sound is muffled.

Open string sounds should be clear, resonating and as noiseless as possible. Various sources identified the importance of the use of nails, the simplicity of movements, and the angle of attack on producing the ideal sound. During outward plucking (away from player), it is advised to minimize the nail-string contact region and contact time, maintain an upright position, and steer the attack towards the soundboard as opposed to the sky. During inward plucking, it is advised to balance the use of nail and flesh at attack time and avoid violent sounds. The suitable positions of attack along the string differ according to techniques and desired dynamics. In general, upper strings, attack positions close to YueShan produce sharper and more powerful sounds, while lower and attack positions away from YueShan produce soft and harmonious sounds. We chose finger use, pluck position and directionality as gestural subtechnique for open string plucks. Additionally, we include several special open string pluck techniques and erroneous gestures, summarized in Table 1.

2.2 Harmonics 泛声

凡取泛声，多靠岳取，两手齐下，无按有力。

Directions	Outward, inward
Fingers	Thumb, index, middle, ring
Positions	10.8 cm from YueShan, Hui 1, 2, 4 · 3/7, 6
Other techniques	Che 掣, Ti 2 提, Qiao 敲, Zhuoqi 抓起, Daiqi 带起
Erroneous	Deep pluck, Skyward pluck, Prolonged attack, Tilt pluck

Table 1. Open string gestural subtechniques and variations. Clarifications on special techniques: Che: right middle finger nail presses down the string until the string slips away; Ti 2: right middle finger rapidly hooks from below the string and release; Qiao: right index finger flicks the string; Zhuoqi: left thumb lightly lifts string; Daiqi: left ring finger lightly lifts string.

When executing harmonics, right hand attacks close to YueShan. Two hands should coordinate well and act simultaneously, there is force even without pressing.

泛声谓之徽声，徽正则鸣，徽差则塞，需要指正当徽，用按不着琴面，浮于弦上点泛。

Harmonics need to be activated at the exact markings (hui) with upright left fingers. Missing the markings can cause muffled sounds. Left hand hovers above the string and activates lightly the harmonics without touching the instrument body.

按而不起，则声不发，按而不着，则声不成，如蜻蜓点水，落而复翔之意。

If left hand attacks and does not lift up immediately, then the sound does not sustain long. If the left hand attacks at the wrong position, then the sound is not there. The left hand needs to be like dragonfly tapping on a body of water, dips down and immediately ready to fly again.

Harmonics are meant to be lightly activated by left finger. Through temporarily dampening the vibration at a given point, it pronounces all the partials sharing the same zero-crossing point. In the treatise, it is advised for the left hand to strike precisely at the given markings, minimize contact time, and balance the force of attack. The right hand is suggested to pluck close to Yueshan, in order to produce sharp sounds with long resonance. The Left and right hand need precise time coordination. When one is slower than the other, the harmonics would not be as much pronounced. We choose finger, position, directionality as gestural subtechniques, along with a few pairs of sounds to investigate the timbral difference elicited by harmonics of the same pitch but activated at different string and hui positions. We include sounds resulting from erroneous gestures such as missed marking, delayed left hand and delayed right hand. Lastly, we record a full set of between-hui harmonics on string 1. Even though *Tang Chenzhuo Zhifa* instructed players to activate only harmonics on precisely the markings, other sources have hinted at the existence of bright and dark “Ming Hui 明徽 / An Hui 暗徽”, summing to up to 31 positions [11].

2.3 Double Notes 双音

声法双音：有上散一弦，下按一弦；或上按一弦，下散一弦；或作上泛一弦，下散一弦；或作上泛一弦，下按一弦作；有双散，双泛，双按作者。

Double notes can have combinations of different techniques. One possibility is to have open and pressed note on the upper and lower string; or the reverse of that; or harmonics and open note on the upper and lower string; or harmonics and pressed note on the upper and lower string; or double open note, double harmonics note and double pressed notes.

Double notes can be either produced by the same mode, or a mix of two different modes of excitation. We cover each of these combinations in the dataset to offer opportunity to distinguish their timbral characteristics.

2.4 Vibrato 颤音

取声指法（吟）有七：吟，振，蹙，敏，偷吟，二撼，摇指，圈附。

There are seven methods of Yin (vibrato): yin (simmering vibrato), zhen (abrupt vibrato), cu (dense vibrato), min (vivid vibrato), touyin (sneaky vibrato), erhan (swinging vibrato), yaozhi (oscillating vibrato), quanfu (circular vibrato)

偷吟：乘声猛按定，不令声散，动而似不动也。Touyin: as right hand pluck the string, left hand firmly press onto the string and perform slight vibrato in great control. the vibrato amplitude is close to imperceptible

圈附：当徽按弦，用指面圆转一遭。如水影摇花之势。

Quanfu: left finger belly press string at the marking, anchoring at the contact point while rotating in circle, like small ripples in a water pond perturbing reflections of the flowers.

声用：用按：按指实则弦振木而发声，有丁清韵也。谓之丝木之声。

When pressing firm and steady, string vibrates against the wood allowing full transmission of the vibration, producing sound that is clear and bright. This is the so-called silk-wood sound.

声用：单按：用吟有二：一法乘声吟，不待

按定成声便吟。一法见声吟，又名声后吟，后无见声，按指方吟。吟罢有少息，更存余韵，方作后声。

Two distinctions of vibratos: *chengshengyin*: simultaneous vibrato and attack, left hand movements for pitch modulations precede the sound takes form; *jianshengyin/shenghouyin*: vibrato after sound during its fading, brief pause after the vibrato to allow lingering resonance of the string to settle, only then would one proceed to the next note.

Vibratos are distinguished by their timing (before or after attack, therefore revealing the beginning pitch or not), modulation frequency, modulation amplitude, vibrato direction (upward or downward pitch first), ways of modulation (sliding left to right, not sliding at all, or circular motion), and pressing mode (nail 甲 *jia*, flesh 肉 *rou*, or half-nail half-flesh 甲肉 *jiarou*). Instead of covering every single technique, we pick the most distinct techniques based on their underlying modalities. The chosen techniques are attack-vibrato (*Chengshengyin* 乘声吟), resonance-vibrato (*Shenghouyin* 声后吟), still-vibrato (*Dingyin* 定吟), sneaky-vibrato (*Touyin* 偷吟), and circular-vibrato (*Quanfu* 圈附). We record two sets of vibratos around string 4 Hui 9 and string 7 Hui 4. Each set includes all aforementioned techniques executed with nail pressing, flesh pressing and nail-flesh pressing. The first set is of lower pitch performed with *Gou* (right middle finger inward pluck), whereas the second set is of high pitch performed with *Tiao* (right index finger outward pluck). This string /pitch height/ right hand technique pairing is customary in *guqin* repertoire to optimize both ergonomics and sonic resonance. We therefore include representative vibratos in distinct pitch ranges to acknowledge the possible timbral differences brought by pitch.

2.5 Glissando 滑音

绰注取声，需低腕指，打附弦面，勿令手高，又不可造作，摇身作势。

During glissando attack, right hand and wrist should remain low while finger attacks the string from close by. Avoid postures that are overly dramatic and pretentious.

Glissandos, similar to vibratos, are distinguished by its timing, velocity and amplitude. We record three sets of glissandos on string 4 hui 9, string 5 hui 10 and string 7 hui 4. Each set contains variations on timing (before attack and after attack), speed (fast and slow), and amplitude (long and short). The first set uses left thumb and the latter two sets use left ring finger. Meanwhile, the first two sets use *Gou* (right middle finger inward pluck) whereas the last set uses *Tiao* (right index finger outward pluck). Again this combination is based on physical ergonomics and its frequent occurrences in traditional *guqin* repertoire.

3. DATASET DESIGN AND ACQUISITION

3.1 Design

We establish a few gesture–timbre hypotheses that will be examined closely. For example, we hypothesize that the position of plucking and directionality has an impact on the timbres of open string plucks, whereas finger used during plucking does not. This prompts us to design a dataset that have graded or binary variability in each gestural sub-techniques while keeping the rest of the gestural attributes intact. In other words, a subset of samples for studying the impact of each gestural subtechnique on each playing technique are available. These samples are also kept as much as possible to be on the same string or pitch height. To define the specific choices of variability, we balance the size of the combinatorial problem, and practicality of the gestural variant in the musical context. We are fortunate to invite *qin* master Dr. Liyu You to both provide us feedback on the musical relevance and physical feasibility of our designed dataset, and execute these sounds in the best effort of her rigor and precision. The final version of the dataset is a result of iterative discussions and revisions between the author and Liyu You. Each playing technique is repeated three times to both enlarge the dataset size and take into account the inter-take variability.

3.2 Acquisition

We define a ladder of gestural data at various levels of detail, ranging from discrete labels of playing techniques, the aforementioned degrees of freedom to continuous signals acquired by high-speed camera with machine learning based hand-tracking system. The audiovisual material we collected composes recordings from two microphones, footages from three cameras and signals from three accelerometers. During the recording session, we place two 60 frames per second (fps) GoPro cameras (Hero 4) on either sides of the *qin* to capture detailed movements on each hand. We place one 25 fps Canon XF 300 camera in front to capture the frontal view of the *qin*. One condenser microphone Neumann KM184 is positioned above the instrument, and one Schertler Dyn-C-P48 contact microphone is stucked onto the bottom of the *qin* soundboard to capture sound transmitted through air and structural vibrations respectively. Additionally, we adopt an experimental method to measure the force exerted by left hand during portamento and vibrato. Specifically, we tape two accelerometers (Piezoelectric 352A24/352C22) onto the thumb and ring finger of left hand, and one accelerometer (Piezoelectric 356A15) onto the bottom of the soundboard. We postulate that a high correlation between the finger and sound board accelerometer signal indicates a strong binding between the finger and instrument, therefore a larger force exertion. The dataset results in 514 paired multichannel audio and video files, summing to about three hours of audiovisual material.

3.3 Perceptual studies

Data-driven correlation studies risk uncovering spurious correlations. If two sounds are indistinguishable even to an

Playing technique	Degrees of freedom	Samples
Open string	RH position, finger use, directionality, excitation mode	136
Harmonics	LH position, point of contact, hand coordination	201
Vibrato	LH position, point of contact, amplitude, frequency, force, timing	45
Portamento	LH position, point of contact, amplitude, speed, force, timing	50
Double notes	two modes out of [open string, harmonics, pressed string]	83

Table 2. Selected playing techniques, their identified gestural subtechniques from ancient text, and the number of samples collected in the dataset. “RH” and “LH” stand for “right hand” and “left hand”.

Figure 2. Recording Session setup. From left to right are views from the Canon and GoPro cameras located on the right and left side of the qin.

expert’s ear, is it still meaningful to study how their underlying gestures differ and influence the sound-production? For this reason, concurrent studies of perception-driven sanity checks should be carried out to inform the validity of data-driven approaches. With Liyu, we have launched a listening test probing expert musician’s ability to distinguish pluck position from sounds. Specifically, she was presented with 67 pairs of open string sounds and their respective playing techniques (indicating the finger used and directionality) and asked to select which one of the two sounds is plucked closer to the bridge. The results indicate that pluck position’s proximity to bridge is indeed identified correctly by an expert: with 94% accuracy in the case of Liyu. Due to time constraints, the perceptual study was conducted on a single musician and did not encompass the full range of gestural subtechniques. However, the results highlight the capability of embodied listening in expert musicians and pave the way for a more comprehensive study to explore the limit of gestural implications in musical timbre.

4. EXPERIMENTS

4.1 Intra-class distance

After collecting such paired data of qin gestures and timbres, we numerically validate their variability (or invariability). Treating each gesture as a discrete class, contrasting intra-class and inter-class distances is a straightforward method to quantify the extent of sonic differences underlying gestural variations. We adopt constant-Q transform (CQT) coefficients as time-frequency feature and use its euclidean distance as the metric space. The CQT filterbank spans eight octaves with a minimum center frequency at 32.7 Hz and twelve filters per octave. We keep 10 time bins of post-attack coefficients (equivalent to 0.2 seconds) and compute its temporal average to represent each sample.

Figure 3 demonstrates the intra-class distance distributions of selected open string, harmonics and double note

samples. On the top are distributions of pairwise distances across all selected samples within each category. The smaller the intra-class distances are contrasting the top distance distribution, the more defining classes they form. Among the three gestural subtechniques for open string: position, finger used and directionality, sounds with the same pluck position elicit the smallest intra-class distance, therefore indicating its significance in pluck string timbre. One can also observe from Figure 3 (b) that harmonics samples of the same pitch but different positions are spectrally distinct. While right hand position contributed further to spectral characteristics, the effects of right finger use and directionality are close to negligible. Lastly, Figure 3 (c) shows that different composition of double note techniques elicit spectral difference. Among them, double open string is the most distinct from others.

4.2 Isomap dimensionality reduction

Distribution of distance measures reflect only pairwise relationship. To be able to contextualize each sound in a repertoire requires constructing multidimensional timbre spaces whose topology reflects the perceptual distance between distinct samples. To this aim, we adopt the same CQT coefficients and Isomap to organize frame-wise samples of sounds concerning each hypothesis into a three dimensional timbre space. Isomap composes a nearest neighbor graph computation and multidimensional scaling (MDS) [12]. The samples are placed closer if their time-frequency descriptors are close in euclidean space and vice versa. We color the samples based on their underlying gestural labels and observe the separability and definition of clusters formed by samples of the same color. Figure 4 shows an example of the timbre space formed by all open string pluck sounds. Here, a given gestural subtechnique’s impact on timbre is equated to a measure of separability. Qualitatively, one may look at the colored samples on Isomap and instantly tell definition of the clusters formed. Quantitatively, silhouette coefficients, Calinski–Harabasz Index and Davies–Bouldin Index are variants of metrics

Figure 3. Distributions of intraclass distances between selected samples. (a) Open string plucks. All sounds are plucked with right hand on one of 5 positions on string 4, using one of four fingers, with outward or inward directionality. (b) Harmonic sounds. The samples selected are all executed in correct manner (instead of erroneous) and could be from different strings, left and right hand positions, fingers, and pluck directionality. From the second row downward, samples are cumulatively constrained to having more and more identical subtechniques. (c) Double notes plucked by right thumb and index. All samples are executed with one of six double note techniques: pp (both pressed), oo (both open), hp (harmonic and pressed), ho (harmonic and open), hh (both harmonic).

that measure the ratio between mean pairwise inter- and intra-class samples distances, which reflect separability of classes without supervision [13, 14]. Additionally, we color the samples with both customized and common audio descriptors to aid interpreting the spatial arrangements physically. Specifically, these descriptors include frame-wise RMS energy, time after onset attack, spectral flatness, spectral centroid, and spectral bandwidth.

With such general pipeline of hypothesis building, data visualization and evaluation, we arrive at the following conclusions:

- (a) Among the three gestural subtechniques for open string sounds, pluck positions form the most defined clusters and is thus the most influential on timbre. Finger use has the least influence. Directionality forms defined sub-clusters within the clusters of each pluck position and is more influential than finger use.
- (b) The same observations above for open string sounds apply to harmonics sounds.
- (c) Among the common erroneous gestures of right hand pluck are skyward pluck (when the suffix of outward pluck ends upwards instead of downwards to the soundboard), tilt pluck (when the finger, nail or flesh, lands on the string with a roll rotation), press pluck (when outward pluck is not fast enough resulting in a press-and-pluck motion), and deep pluck (when the nail cuts deep on the string during outward plucking). Skyward pluck has noticeably less energy than the rest of erroneous modes and thus is the most separable on timbre map. Meanwhile, the samples with the highest spectral flatness (the noisiest/most disparate from pure tone) come from frames of skyward pluck and tilt pluck in early attack time.

(d) Press pluck and deep pluck are indistinguishable spectrally.

(e) Harmonics of the same pitch and right hand position, but activated on different strings and left hand positions are separable on Isomap.

(f) Among the erroneous harmonic sound gestures are off-hui (when left hand misses the correct harmonics-inducing position), late lift (when left finger does not lift up quickly enough), mis-coordination (when left finger strikes later than right finger pluck). All erroneous modes are spectrally distinct. Late lift and mis-coordination have faster decay reflected in frame-wise RMS energy.

4.3 Discussions and future work

The results above are conclusive within the scope of the proposed methodology. But many choices on analysis are made along the way, which upon changing, could potentially lead to different results. In this section we hope to bring attention to the limitations and instabilities of these findings and offer insights on how to move forward. Specifically we wish to stress the influence of the adopted analytic tools and data representations have on the findings.

Using Isomap allows validating simple hypothesis via visually compelling spatial relationships formed in multi-dimensions. Yet, neither the quantitative nor qualitative measures can demonstrate beyond the notion of separability. That is, no implication of causality nor the cause of separability can be identified. The maps only get to gain some degree of interpretability when viewed in conjunction with the same map colored by interpretable audio descriptors. An alternative approach would be to target comparing specific aspects of sound and draw conclusions accordingly. The two approaches bring forth a trade off

Figure 4. Visualization of open string sounds in GuqinSonGest after CQT feature extraction and Isomap dimensionality reduction. The number of neighbors in Isomap adopted is 20. Colors denote pluck positions along the string (left), directionality (center), and finger used for plucking (right). “Hui” refers to the mark position. “Hui 0” is 10 cm from the bridge and “Hui 6” is at exactly the middle of the effective string length. From the Isomap we observe that pluck position is the most salient factor for distinguishing open string timbres. The binary pluck direction also forms defined clusters but within those corresponding to each pluck position. On the contrary, finger use coloring elicits the least separability on the timbre map.

between explainability and adaptivity. On one hand for Isomap, audio disparities are summarized by the Euclidean distance between the adopted audio features — in this case CQT coefficients, therefore not interpretable. Yet, the adjacency matrix for nearest-neighbor graph computation takes into account all pairwise audio distances in the dataset. The resulting spatial relationships always adapt and prioritize the most distinguishing factor of sounds within the dataset. For example, frame-wise multiphonic harmonics sounds of different pitches result in a radial pattern of dots, with the radius indicating energy level and angle indicating pitch classes. Frame-wise samples of the same pitch open string sounds in Figure 4 has spectral distribution and energy as the principle axes of the map. Interestingly, the spatial arrangement according to spectral disparities does not conform to physical proximity: the farthest apart pluck position does not necessarily result in the most disparate timbres. This adaptivity can be viewed as both a blessing and a potential source of instability. As the choice of time-frequency descriptor, the samples chosen, the hyper-parameters used for nearest-neighbor graph computation would all play a role in creating a unique timbre map and thereby influence the findings. On the contrary, pairwise sonic analysis with curated samples compromises automation of comparisons with better explainability.

A better approach of demonstrating multimodal data relationship with both adaptivity and explainability require further preprocessing. A promising direction to take is with canonical-correlation analysis (CCA). The idea is to exploit the continuous gestural signals in the videos and obtain pairs of temporal audio-gestural data. CCA then learns linear transformations on top of the paired audio and gestural data respectively, such that maximum cross-correlation is achieved. The learned linear transformations/spatial-

temporal filters can be further interpreted via forward modeling or fast fourier transform (FFT) analysis [15]. This direction is not carried out with the currently assembled data, due to a lack of accurately tracked finger motion data and proper camera calibration. Yet, we believe in the future with better data quality the method offers valuable results.

5. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented GuqinSonGest, a multimodal gesture–timbre dataset of guqin playing techniques. GuqinSonGest is designed by extracting from an ancient treatise historical accounts on the canonical playing gestures and desirable timbral aesthetics. Five sound types are covered, where under each gesture subtechniques are systematically varied to provide opportunities to study the individual influence they have on qin timbre. Through a case study on the gesture–timbre relationship in qin playing techniques, we have demonstrated the varying amount of influences that numerous gestural subtechniques have on the resulting timbre. Our approach employed interclass distance measures and multidimensional timbre maps to visualize the separability of sounds produced by different gestures. Future work should focus on improving video and motion capture quality to enable the investigation of more adaptive and fine-grained multimodal correlations.

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